

Bringing Museums to Virtual Life: ExPresS XR as a No-Code Tool for XR Exhibition Development

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Introduction

Communicating research findings to a broader, often non-specialist public is a central component of scholarly work in archaeology, art history, and historical studies. For these disciplines, the release of the HTC Vive in 2016 - the first consumer-grade head-mounted display (HMD) virtual reality (VR) system with sensor-based tracking - marked a major expansion of the media portfolio for knowledge dissemination (Barnard 2024). This development enabled users to navigate virtual spaces freely, catalyzing the adoption of VR in museums and resulting in a growing number of VR-enhanced exhibitions (Ingrum 2022).

The success of this medium is largely attributed to its immersive nature, which surpasses traditional PC-based systems. As noted by Hepperle and Wölfel (2023), VR is particularly suited for conveying processes that are difficult or impossible to replicate in the real world, such as transporting participants “back in time.” The broader concept of Extended Reality (XR) has since emerged, encompassing Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR).

Driven by technological progress and compelling examples of XR in museum education, XR is now recognized as a key tool in contemporary museum practice (Kaysers and Kollar 2020). These technologies support modern knowledge transfer by enabling content adaptation to diverse audiences, fostering participation, promoting inclusion, and

increasing outreach through open-source distribution. Especially noteworthy is XR’s interactive potential, which allows users to engage with digital artifacts in ways not possible in traditional exhibitions - such as handling, rotating, scaling, or even virtually “throwing” them. This interactivity transforms visitors from passive observers to active participants.

In our daily practice, we often observe that, despite high subject-matter expertise and strong interest in media, both instructors and students frequently lack the technical skills to develop XR applications. To address this, we initiated the project ExPresS XR: Experimentation and Presentation for Science with OpenXR¹. Built on the Unity game engine², ExPresS XR leverages its WYSIWYG (What-You-See-Is-What-You-Get) editor to facilitate 3D environment creation, and extends it with predefined, configurable components for VR development. No programming knowledge is required for standard exhibition scenarios, though the framework remains extensible for more complex projects. It also includes guided dialogs for basic scene configuration to ensure compatibility. ExPresS XR has already been used in several educational and scientific projects with humanities students.

In the following sections, we provide an overview of the ExPresS XR framework, present two example projects, and reflect on best practices and future work based on our experiences.

ExPresS XR

The ExPresS XR framework has been in development at the University of Tübingen since 2022. It builds on Unity’s native support for the OpenXR standard³, which ensures compatibility with a wide range of XR hardware - an essential advantage, particularly in educational contexts. The framework is designed so that common functionality required for VR exhibitions can be created using dialogs and Unity’s visual editor. As the foundation of the framework, Unity, offers a wide range of game-development features; compared to other 3D-modelling solutions such as Blender 3D⁴, Cinema 4D⁵, or Autodesk Maya⁶, this allows the integration of more interactive and playful elements. Moreover, if specific dynamic functionality is not available by default, developers can extend the framework by implementing additional features via Unity’s coding layer. In the following, we present the currently stable functionality available in ExPresS XR.

Given its disciplinary origins, the framework was first used to create virtual museum exhibitions designed to replicate real-world environments. Accordingly, ExPresS XR includes a range of user-guided dialogs to support the creation of essential foundational elements, such as rooms (Fig. 1 (a)), customizable interactive display cases (Fig. 1 (b)), and scene navigation via teleportation.

Fig. 1: Interface of the Unity game engine showing (a) the Room Creator and (b) the Display Case dialog.

Display cases are a central component of exhibition design within the framework. Generic templates are provided, enabling the integration of different types of exhibits (e.g., 3D models, 2D graphics) alongside contextual information in various formats such as text, audio guides, or video, all easily added via graphical input forms.

Once inserted into a display case, objects become immediately interactive: users can pick them up, rotate them, or even throw them. To improve user experience dropped objects are automatically returned to their original position in the display case after a short delay. Each case is also equipped with simple button-based controls that allow users to trigger associated descriptive content.

Beyond features replicating real-world exhibition settings, ExPresS XR also includes engaging and freely configurable game elements. These include quizzes, logic puzzles, and mini-games such as a Whac-A-Mole-style activity where users must hit specific targets in short time to score points.

Particularly due to its relevance in historical contexts, archery mechanics were also implemented. A standard bow can be inserted into the scene and operated using both hands. Customization of both bow and arrows is possible via graphical dialogs, and Unity's physics engine allows for a partially realistic simulation of physical behavior. To embed archery meaningfully into interactive narratives, a variety of target types were created, including both static and dynamic setups. All target types feature a game timer and a scoring system.

To support role-playing and puzzle-solving elements typical of gamified learning, the framework includes components for item collection, combination, and delivery. These support structured interaction design in VR and due to its generalized structure, this mechanic can be easily adapted for various narrative and puzzle-based applications.

For teaching and research purposes, ExPresS XR also includes a flexible data logging system that captures user interactions and behaviors within the XR environment. The system can record, for example, which objects were picked up or dropped, how users answered quiz questions and their reaction times, or the navigational paths taken through the scene. The resulting data are stored in CSV format, enabling easy integration with standard statistical analysis tools. Data can be saved locally or transmitted to external servers via web-based connections, depending on the specific requirements of the research scenario.

Practical Experiences

Temple Tax & Doves

The exhibition *Temple Tax & Doves* was the first large-scale project developed using ExPresS XR. It originated as a collaboration between the departments of Ancient Numismatics, New Testament Studies, and the MA specialization in Digital Humanities at the University of Tübingen. The virtual exhibition enables visitors to immersively explore a 3D reconstruction of Herod's Temple in ancient Jerusalem (Fig. 2 (a)).

Fig. 2: Temple Tax & Doves: (a) Reconstructed temple area (b) Numismatics content (c) Dove trader

The temple model was reconstructed based on the work of (Schwartz and Peleg 2011, 69–90), with the temple's *opus sectile* flooring informed by data from the Mount Sifting Project⁷, as well as research by (Tilly and Zwickel 2015) and (Snyder et al. 2016, 49–58). Through interactive and game-based elements, users engage with the role of coinage in the temple during the time of Jesus (Fig. 2 (b)). Activities include exchanging foreign currency at the money changers' tables to pay the temple tax and purchasing doves as sacrificial offerings (Fig. 2 (c)).

Following its premiere at the Museum of the University of Tübingen MUT in December 2023, the exhibition became a traveling installation and has since been presented in museums across Germany, Austria, Switzerland, South Africa, and China. Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through SFB 1391 at the University of Tübingen, the project was published on *itch.io*⁸ to ensure free public access in line with open research principles.

Hetepheres Tomb VR

Another major project developed with ExPresS XR is *Hetepheres Tomb VR*, which invites users to travel back to Egypt in 1925. There, the famous Egyptologist George Reisner and his team accidentally discovered the tomb of Hetepheres I, mother of Pharaoh Khufu, builder of the Great Pyramid. The project was developed in collaboration between the Institute for Ancient Near Eastern Studies and the MA specialization in Digital Humanities at the University of Tübingen, along with the Department of Near Eastern Languages and Civilizations at Harvard University.

Fig. 3: Hetepheres Tomb VR: (a) Excavation gameplay (b) Site documentation (c) Throne reconstruction

Based on the research of (Manuelian 2023), the VR experience allows visitors to actively reenact the excavation process (Fig. 3 (a)) and engage with open scientific questions - such as why the discovered sarcophagus was empty. Interactions include documenting the excavation through virtual photography (Fig. 3 (b)), unearthing artifacts within the tomb, and reconstructing the golden throne of Hetepheres I using modern tools (Fig. 3 (c)), following the 2016 reconstruction by Manuelian and his team⁹.

The exhibition premiered at the MUT Tübingen in July 2025 and is scheduled to be hosted at the Harvard Museum of the Ancient Near East in early 2026. In addition to its use in teaching, the application has been published free of charge on the Meta Quest App Store¹⁰ and on Steam¹¹, in accordance with open data principles.

Best Practices & Future Work

Based on our experiences showcasing these VR applications within museum contexts, we have identified a series of best practices as well as open research questions, which are discussed in the following.

First, our observations support the requirements for VR exhibitions identified by (Shehade et al. 2020), namely: (1) interactions must be kept as simple as possible due to visitors' highly heterogeneous prior experience with VR, and (2) additional staff support is essential to guide users through the experience. Although motion sickness was cited by the study as a major concern, this issue was only rarely reported in our own field settings. This may be attributed to the use of Meta Quest headsets, combined with our integration of motion-sickness reducing techniques during development - such as field-of-view reduction (Fernandes and Feiner 2016, 201-210), avoidance of automatic movement, and teleportation-based navigation (Chang, Kim and Yoo 2020, 1658-1682).

While visitors consistently described the visual environments as exciting and impressive, they tended to spend more time exploring interactive elements - particularly when these allowed for freedom of action, such as the ability to throw or manipulate artifacts. This tendency was especially pronounced when gameplay was streamed to accompanying peers, who often offered encouragement, suggestions, or instructions, adding a social dynamic to the experience.

Nonetheless, our exhibitions also revealed that visitors would benefit from improved onboarding tutorials, ideally integrated directly into the VR experience. In our current implementations, instructions were primarily provided via text dialogs in the main menu and through pre-playtime explanations by staff. While this was generally sufficient, it became unmanageable in larger groups due to the need for one-on-one support. We therefore identify a clear need for further research into intuitive and scalable onboarding methods for VR exhibition settings.

One promising direction - both for in-game tutorials and for conveying exhibition content involves the integration of avatar-based chat assistants. We are currently developing such an extension for ExPresS XR, enabling developers to integrate large language model (LLM) APIs into the application. Within defined areas of the virtual exhibition, visitors will be able to interact with a voice-activated chatbot. User questions will be translated into LLM requests, and responses will be delivered via synthesized voice output, maintaining a high level of immersion.

Another significant extension under development is multiplayer functionality for XR exhibitions. In discussions with museum curators, the ability for staff to join multiple visitors in the virtual environment - interacting, pointing to objects, and guiding exploration in real time - was consistently identified as a valuable feature. Such multiplayer capability could also improve accessibility for individuals unable to physically attend museums and enable the development of cooperative, team-based experiences such as escape rooms, role-playing games, and collaborative learning scenarios.

However, these approaches raise further research questions regarding usability and user acceptance. Future work will need to assess how these new features affect the learning experience, visitor satisfaction, and operational feasibility in real-world museum contexts.

Conclusion

The development and integration of extended reality (XR) applications into museum exhibitions presents a range of challenges, particularly for institutions with limited technical resources. In this paper, we introduced *ExPresS XR* as a framework that enables the creation of XR exhibitions without the need for programming. We presented two example projects developed using the tool and reflected on best practices as well as future development directions.

We hope that this contribution will support and inspire others who plan to implement their own XR exhibitions within museum contexts.

Footnotes

1. The project is published under MIT licence on GitHub: <https://github.com/eisclimber/ExPresS-XR>, last access 31.07.25

2. <https://unity.com>, last access 31.07.25
3. <https://www.khronos.org/openxr/>, last access 31.07.25
4. <https://www.blender.org/>, last access 31.07.25
5. <https://www.maxon.net/de/cinema-4d> , last access 31.07.25
6. <https://www.autodesk.com/de/products/maya> , last access 31.07.25
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8. <https://eisclimber.itch.io/temple-tax-and-doves>, last access 31.07.25
9. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wzySMQrM6RA>, <https://skfb.ly/oKr9S>, last access 31.07.25
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